

The Impact of CAD/CAM Technology in Modern Dentistry

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Abstract: *The rapid advancements in computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) technology have revolutionized the field of dentistry. This thesis explores the profound impact of CAD/CAM technology on modern dental practice, focusing on its applications, benefits, and implications for both clinicians and patients.*

Keywords — CAD/CAM system, dentistry, digital modeling, dental restorations, accuracy, efficiency, patient care.

Introduction:

Over the past 20 years, computer-aided design (CAD)/computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) has become more common in dentistry. Inlays, onlays, veneers, crowns, fixed partial dentures, implant abutments, and even full-mouth reconstruction can be done with this method. It is used in dental offices and dental laboratories. CAD/CAM is also used in orthodontics. The development of CAD/CAM technology was motivated by three challenges. The first challenge was making sure the fix was robust enough, especially for posterior teeth. The creation of restorations that seemed natural presented the second challenge. The final challenge involved making tooth repair easier, quicker, and more accurate. Due to CAD/CAM technology, patients occasionally get restorations on the same day. Dentists and laboratories may use the new technology in a variety of ways. Dentists can either perform their own internal CAD and milling, or they can build a digital image and submit it to a lab for manufacturing restorative materials. When laboratories get a digital impression, they can use the information to create a stone model, which can then either be used as is for traditional production or rescanned for milling. As an alternative, the lab can complete all of the design work online using the photos obtained.

The use of Computer-Aided Design/Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAD/CAM) systems in dentistry has revolutionized the way dental professionals design and fabricate dental restorations. This innovative technology has significantly improved the accuracy, efficiency, and quality of dental care, leading to better patient outcomes and satisfaction. It has been using for different dental purposes. It streamlines the traditional workflows by reducing the time and effort required to produce high-quality dental restorations.

Benefits of CAD/CAM system in dentistry:

There are numerous advantages of CAD/CAM in dentistry for both dental professionals and patients. It improves the quality of dental restorations, reduces treatment time, enhances patient comfort, and helps to increase the

overall efficiency – and therefore profitability – of dental practices.

Precision and accuracy: Digital scanning reduces the risk of errors and ensures a perfect fit for the restoration. Then CAD software enables Avant technicians to make precise adjustments to achieve optimal aesthetics and functionality.

Enhanced patient experience: Digital dentistry eliminates the use of traditional impression materials that can be quite uncomfortable for patients. CAD/CAM digital dentistry also streamlines the entire restoration workflow, and reduces appointment and waiting time for patients.

Superior aesthetics: CAD/CAM restorations can be highly customized to closely match the patient's natural teeth. CAD software enables Avant technicians to precisely manipulate shapes, sizes, and shades to create restorations that blend seamlessly with the patient's smile.

Improved efficiency: Digital scans can typically be completed faster than physical impressions, which means less chair time and shorter appointments per patient. CAD/CAM dentistry also drastically reduces the need for remakes – and associated expenses.

The whole process could take anywhere from 45 minutes to two hours, depending on the case's complexity. Still, CAD/CAM requires less time and effort than traditional laboratory methods. The process is not so complicating as it looks. It involves:

1. **Tooth Preparation.** Your dental professional will prepare the site for your restoration by removing all decay or portions of the structurally unsound tooth.
2. **Intraoral Scanning.** Next, an optical scanner will digitally capture the tooth preparation and surrounding teeth to create a 3D custom image.
3. **Restoration Design.** With those 3D images, the dental professional will use the CAD software to design the final restoration.
4. **Milling.** Next, a milling machine takes the design and shapes the crown, veneer, inlay, onlay, or bridge from a single block of ceramic.

5. **Sintering and Polishing.** The restoration is stained or glazed to look more natural before being polished.
6. **Cementation.** Finally, the restoration is permanently placed in your mouth to complete your smile.

Due to the comfortability and easy way of making dental restorations, there are some exact differences from traditional way of treating teeth. Chairside CAD/CAM restoration typically creates and lutes(bonds) the prosthesis the same day. Conventional prostheses, such as crowns, have temporaries placed for one to several weeks while a dental laboratory or in-house dental lab produces the restorations. The patient returns later to have the temporaries removed and the laboratory-made crown cemented or bonded in place. An in-house CAD/CAM system enables the dentist to create a finished inlay in as little as one hour. CAD/CAM systems use an optical camera to take a virtual impression by creating a 3D image which is imported into a software program and results in a computer-generated cast on which the restoration is designed

Bonded veneer CAD/CAM restorations are more conservative in their preparation of the tooth. As bonding is more effective on tooth enamel than the underlying dentin care is taken not to remove the enamel layer. Though one-day service is a benefit that is typically claimed by dentists offering chairside CAD/CAM services, the dentist's time is commonly doubled and the fee is therefore doubled.

The integration of CAD/CAM technology in dentistry has had a profound impact on the way dental care is delivered, leading to improved outcomes and patient experiences. As CAD/CAM systems continue to evolve and improve, they are expected to play an even more significant role in shaping the future of modern dentistry.

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